

Market Fish Resources in Magallanes, Sorsogon, Philippines

Mark Ariel D. Malto and Richard V. Dumilag*

Fisheries Department, Sorsogon State University – Magallanes Campus,
Aguada Norte, Magallanes, Sorsogon 4705 Philippines

Since the 1930s, a number of fish taxa have been recorded from the marine waters of Magallanes in Sorsogon, Philippines. However, it has only in 1995 that the checklist was properly updated, in which the number of recorded species plummeted but has yet to reach a plateau. While the actual field surveys on natural habitats are a common approach to obtaining fish records, market surveys are also proven equally aidful. Here, we present an updated checklist of all named species of fish vended in Magallanes markets – including their local name, origin, and temporal availability. Sourced from Sorsogon Bay and Ticao-Burias Pass, a total of 77 species were identified. Thirteen species set new records for Sorsogon Bay. The Ticao-Burias Pass was the exclusive source of 11 taxa. A total of 61 species were sourced from either site. The current list of marketed fish from Magallanes represents 20% with that of the entire fish records reported from Sorsogon Bay. The fish species composition varied both in terms of origin and seasonal availability. Comparison of the present list of commercial fish in Magallanes against other records elsewhere in the Philippines may not be possible at the present, as previous studies indicated different sampling efforts, wider area coverage, and longer cumulative observation period. Return efforts and further market survey studies are expected to augment the current number of recorded fish taxa. Our present study makes recommendations for the continued use of market surveys to help update and verify records of fish diversity in a given area.

Keywords: commercial fish, fish distribution, fish seasonality, Sorsogon Bay, Ticao-Burias Pass

Magallanes (Figure 1) is one of the major fishing areas in western Sorsogon in the Philippines. It has an estimated coastline of more than 30 km that constitutes a land mass connected to the municipality of Juban on its eastern side. It has two islands – namely, the Bagatao and Tinacos, both located off the northwestern area intercepting the mouth of Sorsogon Bay. Through the Fisheries Administrative Order 17-17 ser. 1963, Magallanes was officially designated as one of the major fish landings in the Bicol Region. In 1972, Sorsogon Bay, including the waters surrounding Magallanes was declared a conservation area saved from trawl fishing and other destructive methods (Ordoñez *et al.* 1972). There is a rich diversity of fish taxa historically accounted for the area (Herre 1934; Ordoñez

et al. 1972; Cinco and Pamintuan 1995; Cinco and Perez 1995; Cinco *et al.* 1995a, b; Olaño *et al.* 2009; Olaño and Lanzuela 2016; Lanzuela *et al.* 2019). Magallanes is also known as one of the Philippine primary fishing grounds for *Sardinella lemuru* or locally referred to as "lawlaw" (Figure 2). Notwithstanding the fact that fish are the primary source commodity in Magallanes, the list of marketed fish in the area has been at best fragmented.

The history of fish records in Magallanes probably began in the 1930s when Albert William Christian Theodore Herre, the previous Chief of Fisheries of the Bureau of Science in Manila from 1919–1928, listed 18 fish species (Table 1). Herre (1934) also described a new species, *Sorsogona serrulata* (now *Sorsogona tuberculata*) from Magallanes. The next 38 years saw a lack of additional

*Corresponding author: richard.dumilag@sorsu.edu.ph

Figure 1. Map of Magallanes, Sorsogon, Philippines.

Figure 2. Magallanes is one of the fishing grounds of *Sardinella lemuru* (lawlaw) in the Philippines. Piles of *S. lemuru* (a) unloaded in Magallanes jetty ready to be transported elsewhere (b).

Table 1. Checklist of fish taxa collected from Magallanes, Sorsogon in 1930s by Herre (1934).

No.	Family	Current name	Local name	Habitat
1	Anabantidae	<i>Anabas testudineus</i>	Puyo	Dm
2	Apogonidae	<i>Fowleria aurita</i>	Dangat	Rf
3	Blenniidae	<i>Petroscirtes variabilis</i> ^a	Palo	Rf
4	Carangidae	<i>Carangoides chrysophrys</i>	Mamsa	Rf
5	Centriscidae	<i>Centriscus scutatus</i>	Sipul-sipul	Rf
6	Chaetodontidae	<i>Parachaetodon ocellatus</i>	Alibang-bang	Rf
7	Drepaneidae	<i>Drepane punctata</i>	Bayang	Rf
8	Exocoetidae	<i>Parexocoetus brachypterus</i>	Iliw	Pg-n
9	Gobiidae	<i>Glossogobius celebius</i>	Biya	Dm
10	Gobiidae	<i>Parachaeturichthys polynema</i>	Biya	Dm
11	Holocentridae	<i>Neoniphon sammara</i>	Parangan	Rf
12	Labridae	<i>Cymolutes lecluse</i>	Molmol	Rf
13	Labridae	<i>Cymolutes praetextatus</i>	Molmol	Rf
14	Labridae	<i>Halichoeres bicolor</i>	Lawihan	Rf
15	Labridae	<i>Iniistius pentadactylus</i> ^b	Molmol	Rf
16	Menidae	<i>Mene maculata</i>	Timon-timon	Rf
17	Paralichthyidae	<i>Pseudorhombus arsius</i>	Palad	Dm
18	Platycephalidae	<i>Sorsogona tuberculata</i> ^c	Itang	Dm

Originally named as ^a*Petroscirtes eretes*, ^b*Hemipteronotus pentadactylus*, and ^c*Sorsogona serrulata*.
[Dm] demersal; [Pg-n] pelagic-neritic; [Rf] reef-associated

fish records from the area. Since Sorsogon Bay is one of the fishing grounds in Magallanes, records from this body of water are thus directly attributable to what can be found in Magallanes. Prompted by the issue of banning of trawl fishing in Sorsogon Bay, Ordoñez *et al.* (1972) surveyed the site (including market surveys) and have recorded additional 12 fish taxa. In 1995, fish capture studies (data collection began in 1994) around Sorsogon Bay presented 163 taxa (Cinco and Pamintuan 1995; Cinco and Perez 1995; Cinco *et al.* 1995a, b). A stock assessment from fish landing areas was done from April 1999–March 2003 (Olaño *et al.* 2009). This report accounted a total of 234 species; however, the complete list of the surveyed taxa was not included in the report and hence, unavailable for further checklist cross-validation. In 2016, the Resources Environment and Economics Center for Studies, Inc. reported 94 fish species for the bay. Two guidebooks on fish resources in Sorsogon Bay that have been underwritten by the Bureau of Fisheries and Aquatic Resources Region (BFAR) V allowed the inclusion of 124 fish species (Olaño and Lanzuela 2016; Lanzuela *et al.* 2019).

Fish records in Magallanes have traditionally been reported through actual field surveys (*i.e.* observation from natural habitats). However, other approaches such as market surveys were proven to be equally helpful [*e.g.* Ordoñez *et*

al. (1972) and Padin *et al.* (2011)]. The aim, therefore, of this study is to provide an updated species inventory of the current commercial fish vended in Magallanes, including their sources and temporal availability.

In addition to historical records gleaned from the literature published in 1930–2019, the list of common names of vended fish in Magallanes was obtained from the records kept by the LGU units and the local government unit of Magallanes and the BFAR–Provincial Fisheries Office. The generated roster was subsequently validated through a semi-structured survey with vendors, including peddlers in Magallanes. Market surveys were conducted from October 2021–September 2022 (twice a month). The origin of the marketed fish, respective local name, and their temporal availability were determined. Fish were identified down to species level based on gross morphological structure through consulting regional atlases (Carpenter and Niem 1999; Olaño *et al.* 2009; Lanzuela *et al.* 2019; Froese and Pauly 2022). Species names were updated based on FishBase (Froese and Pauly 2022). Frequency of previous fish species records were compared from that of the present list. The species accumulation curve was constructed to demonstrate the cumulative number of fish records over the years. Comparative pairwise records were computed using Sørensen’s similarity index (Sørensen 1948) and visualized through Venn diagrams. The Sørensen’s similarity index is

expressed as $SI = (2N_c) / (N_a + N_b)$, where N_c is the number of species held in common for both sites, whereas N_a and N_b is the sum of fish taxa in each paired sites.

Participated by more than a thousand fishers, capture fishing in 2021 represented 77% of the entire agricultural occupations in Magallanes. According to the Municipal Agriculturist Office, as of December 2021, the total number of registered fish vendors (at times to include peddlers) was 95. The majority were female (66%), with most of them have spent a considerable number of years of selling fish (~ 10 years and above). Today, the central public market in Magallanes is situated in Brgy. Poblacion (12°49'40" N, 123°50'0" E). It opens daily with a heavy foot traffic between 05:00–10:00 AM. Fish are exclusively vended in an area separated from other wet commodities like vegetables and meat. The central public market in Magallanes is less than a kilometer away from the coastal or landing areas. A fish landing center is located in Brgy. Bacolod Pier (12°49'46" N, 123°49'50" E), having two ports and six wharves. The Community Fish Landing Center (CFLC) at Brgy. Central (12°49'32" N, 123°50'40" E) under the Bureau of Fisheries and Aquatic Resources (BFAR) program became operational in November 2021. Fish landed to these centers are transported *via* public utility vehicles directly to the market. Artisanal fishers either vend their goods in the market or sell to fish vendors or traders. The most common type of preservation of fresh fish in Magallanes is through ice storage. At present, there is no operational ice plant available in the area. Fishers usually resorted ice from stores to preserve fish produce.

A total of 77 fish species in Magallanes market (Table 1) were identified. These taxa were distributed in 36 families and 62 genera. In terms of the number of species, the top available fish resources in the area belong to the family Carangidae ($n = 10$), followed by Scombridae ($n = 7$). Carangid fishes (*e.g.* jacks and scads) and scombrids (*e.g.* tunas and mackerels) are widely distributed in tropical seas and are among the most economically important pelagic fishes (Collette *et al.* 2001; Reed *et al.* 2002). Our findings on the most dominant fish group in the market of Magallanes are quite expected as these taxa are also common elements of fish markets elsewhere in the Philippines (Padin *et al.* 2011; Muallil *et al.* 2020).

Sixty-eight (68) local names of market fishes in Magallanes were identified. Most of the vendors refer to the fish (91%) they sell using only a single common name. While it appears that locals in Magallanes can distinguish market fishes matching a distinct species (*i.e.* bearing a separate scientific name), some fish local names can be at times ambiguous. Such a case is seen in seven local names – "agingoy", "baraka", "dalagang bukid", "kanasi", "latab", "manuping", "palad", "punong", "sapsap", "sibubog", "titso", and "turingan" – which represent more than one species (see Table 2).

Two fishing grounds were identified namely the Sorsogon Bay and Ticao-Burias Pass. The latter area was the exclusive source of 11 species (see Table 2). Four species can be sourced restrictedly from Sorsogon Bay – namely, *Arius maculatus*, *Scatophagus argus*, *Siganus canaliculatus*, and *Siganus guttatus*. Sixty-one

Table 2. List of market fish resources in Magallanes, Sorsogon, Philippines, including source information and temporal availability. New records are written in boldfaced.

No.	Family	Species	Local name	Origin	Habitat	Seasonality
1	Acanthuridae	<i>Naso unicornis</i>	Surahan	2	Rf	Y
2	Ariidae	<i>Arius maculatus</i> ^{ab}	Alawon, Kanduli	1	Dm	Y
3	Belonidae	<i>Ablennes hians</i> ^a	Balu	3	Rf	NEM
4	Belonidae	<i>Strongylura leiura</i>	Dual	3	Rf	NEM
5	Caesionidae	<i>Caesio cuning</i>	Dalagang Bukid	3	Pg-n	SWM
6	Caesionidae	<i>Caesio teres</i> ^{ac}	Dalagang Bukid	3	Pg-n	SWM
7	Carangidae	<i>Alepes djedaba</i> ^{abc}	Salay-salay	3	Pg-n	SWM
8	Carangidae	<i>Carangoides coeruleopinnatus</i> ^{ab}	Mamsa	3	Pg-n	NEM
9	Carangidae	<i>Decapterus kurroides</i>	Pulang Buntot	3	Pg-n	Y
10	Carangidae	<i>Decapterus macrosoma</i> ^c	Sibubog	2	Pg-n	Y
11	Carangidae	<i>Decapterus russelli</i>	Sibubog	2	Pg-n	Y
12	Carangidae	<i>Dussumieria elopoides</i> ^{dc}	Tamban	3	Pg-n	NEM
13	Carangidae	<i>Elagatis bipinnulata</i> ^c	Salmon	2	Pg-n	Y
14	Carangidae	<i>Parastromateus niger</i> ^{abc}	Pampano	3	Rf	NEM
15	Carangidae	<i>Selar crumenophthalmus</i> ^{ab}	Matam-baka	3	Pg-n	NEM

Table 2. Cont.

16	Carangidae	<i>Selaroides leptolepis</i> ^{abc}	Dorado	3	Pg-n	Y
17	Clupeidae	<i>Escualosa thoracata</i> ^{ab}	Silag	3	Pg-n	Y
18	Clupeidae	<i>Sardinella fimbriata</i> ^{abc}	Alubaybay	3	Pg-n	NEM
19	Clupeidae	<i>Sardinella lemuru</i> ^{ab}	Lawlaw	3	Pg-n	SWM
20	Cynoglossidae	<i>Cynoglossus abbreviatus</i> ^{abc}	Palad	3	Dm	Y
21	Elopidae	<i>Elops hawaiiensis</i> ^{abc}	Malaguno	3	Pg-n	NEM
22	Engraulidae	<i>Encrasicholina punctifer</i> ^{ab}	Bolinao	3	Rf	SWM
23	Exocoetidae	<i>Cypselurus poecilopterus</i>	Iliw	3	Pg-n	Y
24	Gerreidae	<i>Gerres erythrourus</i> ^{abc}	Latab, Sakalan	3	Dm	NEM
25	Gerreidae	<i>Gerres filamentosus</i> ^{abcd}	Latab, Sakalan	3	Dm	Y
26	Gerreidae	<i>Gerres oyena</i> ^{abc}	Latab	3	Dm	NEM
27	Haemulidae	<i>Plectorhinchus diagrammus</i> ^b	Alatan	3	Rf	Y
28	Haemulidae	<i>Pomadasys argenteus</i> ^{bcd}	Agoot	3	Dm	SWM
29	Hemiramphidae	<i>Hemiramphus far</i> ^{abc}	Bugiw	3	Rf	SWM
30	Hemiramphidae	<i>Hyporhamphus affinis</i>	Balamban	3	Rf	NEM
31	Istiophoridae	<i>Istiophorus platypterus</i>	Malasugi	2	Pg-o	NEM
32	Leiognathidae	<i>Equulites elongatus</i> ^{abc}	Sapsap	3	Dm	SWM
33	Leiognathidae	<i>Equulites leuciscus</i> ^{abcd}	Sapsap	3	Dm	SWM
34	Leiognathidae	<i>Equulites lineolatus</i> ^{acd}	Sapsap	3	Dm	SWM
35	Leiognathidae	<i>Eubleekeria splendens</i> ^{abcd}	Sapsap	3	Dm	SWM
36	Leiognathidae	<i>Leiognathus ruconius</i> ^{abcd}	Tabiros, Karmeling	3	Dm	SWM
37	Leiognathidae	<i>Nuchequula blochii</i> ^{cd}	Sapsap	3	Dm	SWM
38	Leiognathidae	<i>Photopectoralis bindus</i> ^{bcd}	Sapsap	3	Dm	SWM
39	Lethrinidae	<i>Lethrinus harak</i> ^{ab}	Manuping	3	Rf	SWM
40	Lethrinidae	<i>Lethrinus lentjan</i> ^{abc}	Manuping	3	Rf	SWM
41	Lutjanidae	<i>Lutjanus argentimaculatus</i> ^{ab}	Mangagat	3	Rf	Y
42	Lutjanidae	<i>Lutjanus lutjanus</i> ^{ab}	Madarag	3	Rf	NEM
43	Lutjanidae	<i>Megalaspis cordyla</i> ^{abc}	Pak-an	3	Pg-n	Y
44	Menidae	<i>Mene maculata</i>	Timon-timon	2	Rf	NEM
45	Mugilidae	<i>Crenimugil seheli</i> ^{abc}	Araran, Tabudyos	3	Rf	NEM
46	Mugilidae	<i>Mugil cephalus</i> ^{ab}	Balanak	3	Bn	Y
47	Mullidae	<i>Parupeneus barberinus</i> ^{ac}	Agingoy	3	Rf	NEM
48	Mullidae	<i>Upeneus sulphureus</i> ^{abcd}	Agingoy, Saramulyente	3	Dm	NEM
49	Muraenesocidae	<i>Muraenesox bagio</i> ^{ab}	Ubod	3	Dm	Y
50	Nemipteridae	<i>Nemipterus furcosus</i> ^{ab}	Kanasi	3	Dm	SWM
51	Nemipteridae	<i>Nemipterus japonicus</i> ^{abc}	Kanasi	3	Dm	SWM
52	Nemipteridae	<i>Scolopsis bilineata</i> ^{ac}	Punong	2	Rf	Y
53	Nemipteridae	<i>Scolopsis ciliata</i> ^{ab}	Punong	2	Rf	Y
54	Paralichthyidae	<i>Pseudorhombus arsius</i> ^{abc}	Palad	3	Dm	Y
55	Plotosidae	<i>Plotosus canius</i> ^{ab}	Alimusan	3	Dm	NEM
56	Plotosidae	<i>Plotosus lineatus</i> ^{abc}	Iito	3	Rf	SWM
57	Polynemidae	<i>Eleutheronema tetradactylum</i> ^{abc}	Hugaw	3	Pg-n	SWM
58	Priacanthidae	<i>Priacanthus hamrur</i> ^b	Kuwaw	3	Rf	NEM
59	Scaridae	<i>Scarus ghobban</i> ^{ab}	Angol	3	Rf	Y

Table 2. Cont.

60	Scatophagidae	<i>Scatophagus argus</i> ^{abc}	Kikiro	1	Rf	SWM
61	Scombridae	<i>Auxis thazard</i> ^a	Turingan	3	Pg-n	Y
62	Scombridae	<i>Scomberomorus semifasciatus</i>	Rayado	3	Pg-n	Y
63	Scombridae	<i>Thunnus tonggol</i>	Bangkulis	3	Pg-n	NEM
64	Scombridae	<i>Auxis rochei</i>	Turingan	2	Pg-n	Y
65	Scombridae	<i>Rastrelliger brachysoma</i> ^{abc}	Kabalyas	3	Pg-n	SWM
66	Scombridae	<i>Rastrelliger kanagurta</i> ^{abc}	Burao, Buraw	3	Pg-n	NEM
67	Scombridae	<i>Scomberomorus guttatus</i> ^b	Tanguigi	3	Pg-n	NEM
68	Serranidae	<i>Cephalopholis boenak</i> ^{abc}	Baraka	2	Rf	Y
69	Serranidae	<i>Epinephelus merra</i> ^a	Baraka	2	Rf	Y
70	Serranidae	<i>Epinephelus sexfasciatus</i> ^{ab}	Baraka, Lapu-Lapu	3	Rf	SWM
71	Siganidae	<i>Siganus canaliculatus</i> ^{ab}	Bataway	1	Rf	SWM
72	Siganidae	<i>Siganus guttatus</i> ^{abc}	Moblad	1	Rf	SWM
73	Sillaginidae	<i>Sillago aeolus</i> ^{ab}	Oso-os	3	Dm	Y
74	Sphyraenidae	<i>Sphyraena forsteri</i> ^{ab}	Titso	3	Rf	Y
75	Sphyraenidae	<i>Sphyraena jello</i> ^{abcd}	Titso, Bikuda	3	Rf	Y
76	Synodontidae	<i>Saurida tumbil</i> ^{abcd}	Asuos	1	Bn	NEM
77	Trichiuridae	<i>Trichiurus lepturus</i>	Lahing, Langkoy	3	Bn	NEM

^aOlaño and Lanzuela (2016); ^bLanzuela *et al.* (2019); ^cCinco and Pamintuan (1995); Cinco and Perez (1995); Cinco *et al.* (1995a, b); Ordoñez *et al.* (1972)
[1] Sorsogon Bay; [2] Ticao-Burias Pass; [3] both sites
[Bn] benthopelagic; [Dm] demersal; [Pg-n] pelagic-neritic; [Pg-o] pelagic-oceanic; [Rf] reef-associated
[SWM] southwest monsoon (*habagat*); [NEM] northeast monsoon (*amihan*); [Y] year-round

(61) species were recorded for both sites. A total of 36% were classified as reef-associated, 26% were demersal, and 32% were pelagic-neritic. General proportion pattern of fish taxa as to the type of habitat-association was in consonant with other previous reports from elsewhere in the Philippines (Padin *et al.* 2011; Gonzales 2013; Motomura *et al.* 2017).

Fish availability in Magallanes varied seasonally. Twenty-five (25) species were available only during the southwest monsoon (*habagat*), and 24 species vended only during the northeast monsoon (*amihan*). The data for the seasonality of fish taxa in Magallanes' fishing grounds has yet to be completely determined. Only those marketed fishes commercially available to the locals are reported here and, thus, may not be conclusive if to compare with those other reports, which often used *in situ*-based datasets. In the Philippines, species composition of fish per area can be skewed to either season and is highly dependent with complex interplay of extrinsic and intrinsic factors (Bagarinao and Taki 1986; Kohno *et al.* 1999; Abesamis and Russ 2010).

The comparison of the present list with those previous fish records from the fishing grounds of Magallanes is shown in Figure 3. The number of commercial fish recorded for Magallanes was 77. Other fish market taxa

recorded in several areas in the Philippines – such as in Tawi-Tawi (266 spp., Muallil *et al.* 2020), Palawan (159 spp., Gonzales 2013), Negros Oriental (150 spp.; Padin *et al.* 2011), and Panay (139 spp., Motomura *et al.* 2017) – appeared to be higher than what is presented here. It is, however, difficult to compare the current list with other records from elsewhere in the Philippines primarily due to the non-uniformity of sampling efforts. For example, previous studies may have covered a wider area, a longer cumulative observation/collection period, or different survey approach administration (*i.e.* actual site survey *vs.* trawling *vs.* market survey). Assessment of geographical differences in fish diversity in the Philippines based on merely count records can be most likely inadequate. In part, the number of recorded species varied with strong bias toward areas with well-established research communities, where fish are economically important. In Sorsogon, recent fish researches have mostly focused on species-specific questions and production [*e.g.* Olaño *et al.* (2009), Nieves *et al.* (2013), Alba *et al.* (2016), Amano and Mojados (2018)] and less of those of taxonomic listings or of fish biodiversity studies.

As of 2019, 64 species were known available in market areas surrounding Sorsogon Bay, including Magallanes (Ordoñez *et al.* 1972; Cinco and Pamintuan 1995; Cinco and Perez 1995; Cinco *et al.* 1995a, b; Olaño *et al.* 2009;

Figure 3. Proportional Venn diagrams showing the similarity of checklist of fish resources recorded from Sorsogon Bay (a) and those that are vended in the market (b). The pairwise Sørensen's similarity index values for each comparing site are presented as insets.

Figure 4. Cumulative number of fish species reported in Sorsogon Bay over time.

Olaño and Lanzuela 2016; Lanzuela *et al.* 2019). Thirteen (13) species were added to the present list, which all set new records for Sorsogon Bay (see Froese and Pauly 2022).

Accordingly, the current number of fish species (marketed or non-marketed) record in Sorsogon Bay currently stands at 333. Bringing together all the available records, the fish species thriving in Sorsogon Bay did not indicate a plateau yet (Figure 4). It is expected that additional species are potentially to be discovered through further studies, with highlights on market survey as a tool to aid augmenting fish records. Our present study therefore makes recommendation of the continued use of market surveys to help update and verify records of fish diversity in a given locality.

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